

CHANGES IN ELECTROLYTES AND IL-6 LEVELS AT DIFFERENT STAGES OF EXPERIMENTAL HYDRONEPHROSIS

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ABSTRACT

Hydronephrosis currently remains one of the most significant issues in nephrology and urology. The condition is characterized by the gradual dilation of the renal calyceal and pelvic system due to impaired urine outflow, which leads to atrophy of the renal parenchyma and a decrease in its functional capacity. The rising prevalence of hydronephrosis is associated with an increasing number of cases of urolithiasis, tumors of the urinary tract, and strictures, as well as with improvements in imaging diagnostics, which contribute to more frequent detection of the pathology [Ivanov, 2020].

This problem becomes particularly relevant because hydronephrosis often remains asymptomatic in its early stages, leading to delayed medical consultations. Untimely diagnosis significantly increases the risk of developing chronic kidney disease and disability, which has a notable impact on patient quality of life and increases the economic burden on the healthcare system [Petrova, 2021].

Modern treatment methods include both minimally invasive surgical interventions and conservative approaches; however, the choice of optimal management strategy remains a matter of debate. In this regard, studying risk factors, improving early diagnostic methods, and enhancing the effectiveness of therapeutic measures make the investigation of hydronephrosis especially important within contemporary medical practice.

Objective. To study the dynamics of electrolytes and IL-6 levels at different stages of experimental hydronephrosis.

Materials and Methods. The study was conducted in compliance with GLP standards on 30 rats (180–240 g) divided into three groups: intact, sham-operated, and experimental (UUO). Hydronephrosis was induced by unilateral ureteral obstruction under combined anesthesia; in the sham group, the same procedures were performed without ligation. Blood and kidney tissue samples were collected on days 1, 5, and 14. Serum (3000 rpm, 8 min) was analyzed for electrolytes and IL-6 using a HUMALYZER Primus and Scitek EMLR-112. Western blotting was performed on kidney tissue. Statistical analysis was carried out using ANOVA ($p < 0.05$) in GraphPad Prism 8.

Results and Discussion. The results of the biochemical analyses showed that in the sham-operated group, sodium levels remained stable, with only a slight increase on day 5, whereas in the experimental group a sharp rise was recorded by day 14 — up to 516.97 ± 64.82 mmol/L. Potassium levels in all groups stayed within the physiological range: minor decreases on day 5 quickly normalized, and in the experimental group the changes remained minimal ($4.29 \pm 0.53 \rightarrow 4.18 \pm 0.67$ mmol/L). Chloride levels in the control group also returned to normal by day 14, whereas in the hydronephrosis group a marked increase was observed — up to 135.49 ± 25.23 mmol/L.

The dynamics of IL-6 reflected the different degrees of inflammation: in the control group the marker remained stable, in the sham group it showed a moderate rise, while in the experimental group it exhibited a progressive increase from 127.8 ± 18.4 to 190.0 ± 28.5 pg/mL by day 14. This indicates a pronounced inflammatory response in ureteral obstruction and supports IL-6 as a sensitive biomarker of kidney injury.

Conclusions:

1. In the course of experimental hydronephrosis, the rats' electrolyte concentrations varied substantially: during the experiment, sodium and chloride levels increased approximately 2-fold and 1.5-fold, respectively, while potassium ion concentrations remained unchanged.
2. Experimental unilateral obstruction of the pyeloureteral segment in rats leads to a significant elevation of IL-6 levels as early as day 1, with a subsequent increase by days 5 and 14, reflecting the activation of a systemic inflammatory response during the development of hydronephrosis.

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